

PENTAPARTITE GAP ANALYSIS: IMPROVING THE COMPUTER SYSTEM SERVICING SPECIALIZATION OF SELECTED PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF MANILA

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 5

Pages: 579-595

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2176

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13294381

Manuscript Accepted: 07-09-2024

Pentapartite Gap Analysis: Improving the Computer System Servicing Specialization of Selected Public Schools in the Division of Manila

Dominic T. Urgelles,* Marycris V. Urgelles
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

As the educational landscape changes throughout time and with circumstances that forced learning institutions to shift and implement different modalities, maximizing the use of technology in teaching and learning has become an approach to meet the demands of present educational system. This study aimed to investigate the quality of instruction of Computer System Servicing specialization utilizing a strategy called as Pentapartite Gap Analysis; specifically, identifying the issues of learning, utilizing the five key dimensions of the gap analysis which are knowledge, delivery, communication, perception, and service quality to evaluate the said specialization, and proposed an action plan to improve the quality of the specialization across selected public schools. Employing quantitative descriptive research design and utilizing data collection through structured surveys to students and teachers, the study yielded the following results: (1) the respondents perceived the issues faced by the school when first implementing the program in terms of facilities, teachers, and instructional materials; (2) the respondents perceived the extent of the school's capability in offering the specialized program to be at a great extent across various dimensions; and (3) there is a significant difference in the implementation of the said specialization of schools about the assessment of teachers and students. Lastly, there is an importance of an action plan in enhancing the implementation of the specialization program as it served as a strategic guide to strengthen its quality.

Keywords: *Pentapartite Gap Analysis, Computer System Servicing, instruction, technology*

Introduction

The rapid advancement of technology has transformed various aspects of life, including Education. Technology integration in instructional delivery has reshaped the educational landscape, developing specialized programs like Computer System Servicing (CSS) in the Senior High School curriculum (Ventayen, 2018; Villanueva, 2015). As technology becomes increasingly essential, schools must adapt and maximize its use as a tool in Education (Simos et al., 2022; Rogers, 2003). The successful integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Education is vital for preparing students to meet the challenges of the modern workforce (Famor, 2005).

The implementation of Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, introduced the Senior High School program in the Philippines (Department of Education, 2013; DepEd, 2024). This program offers various tracks and strands, including the Information Communication Technology (ICT) strand, encompassing specializations like Computer System Servicing (CSS). In the Division of Manila, particularly in District VI, five out of six senior high schools offer the CSS specialization (Department of Education Manila, 2023). The CSS specialization equips students with knowledge and skills in technology's practical use, application, and management, preparing them for future careers (Llego, 2023; AMA et al. Education, 2021).

However, despite the advantages of the CSS specialization, challenges arise in its implementation. Studies have highlighted the need for contextualized ICT integration practices and continuous review of pedagogical practices to ensure practical and relevant ICT-related practices (Que, 2021; Sindayen & De Leon, 2023). These challenges may impact the knowledge and skills students acquire from their teachers.

A comprehensive review of related literature reveals the importance of ICT integration and its successful innovation in Education (Rogers, 2003; Famor, 2005). However, challenges such as knowledge and skill gaps between students and teachers (Philippine Star, 2005), misplaced teachers and students in the K-12 curriculum (Unwin, 2005), and scarcity of teacher training (Cajilin, 2009) affect the process of instructional delivery. The role of teachers in shaping students' future (Lubian, 2007) and the impact of computers on learning experiences (Wighting, 2006) are also emphasized.

The alignment of educational offerings and practices with industry expectations is crucial for ICT-related courses (Holzweiss et al., 2014; Bates & Santere, 2019). CSS provides new knowledge for students and teachers (Asan, 2003), and assessing 21st-century skills is essential in learning CSS (Oliquino, 2019). Effective communication among teachers, students, and stakeholders contributes to successful program implementation (McCormack et al., 2017), while communication problems can affect graduate employability (Stern, 2015). A conducive learning environment is vital for effective learning (Kincard & Elder, 2005), and a systematic development program is necessary to implement changes (Balwati, 2004).

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- Identify the issues faced by respondents during the initial implementation of the CSS specialization in terms of school facilities, teachers, and instructional materials.

- Measure the extent of the school's capability to offer CSS as a specialization based on the assessment of teachers and students using the Pentapartite Gap Analysis dimensions: knowledge, delivery, communication, perception, and service quality.
- Determine the significant difference in implementing the CSS specialization between the assessment of teachers and students.
- Develop an action plan to improve the implementation of the CSS specialization.

The study adopts the Theory of Needs Analysis by Hutchinson and Waters (1987) as its theoretical foundation. This theory emphasizes the importance of considering learners' needs, potential, and constraints in course design and learning (Juan, 2014). The study also utilizes the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model as its conceptual framework. The input includes the issues faced by respondents during the initial implementation of CSS and the Pentapartite Gap Analysis dimensions. The process involves statistical analysis to identify inferential results based on the gathered data. The output is an action plan for developing the CSS specialization in the selected public schools, leading to a comprehensive and relevant educational experience for students (Ventayen, 2018; Villanueva, 2015; Simos et al., 2022; Rogers, 2003; Famor, 2005).

This study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by addressing the gap and analyzing the five critical dimensions of knowledge: communication, delivery, perception, and service quality in a single model. The proposed action plan, utilizing the Pentapartite Gap Analysis, is expected to improve the CSS specialization in the selected public schools and equip students with the necessary skills to meet the evolving demands of the computer system servicing field.

Literature Review

Pertinent literature that substantiated and supported the findings of this comprehensive analysis. The researchers anchored this comprehensive study to different viewpoints and perspectives to present a thorough treatment of the problem. This covered the literature and past studies relevant to the current study. The literature was focused on the integration of ICT in education along with its importance and opportunities; the challenges faced and experienced during the implementation of ICT-related disciplines; and the key dimensions on the assessment of instructions. This related literature later confirmed, negated, or improved by the new knowledge that this study provides.

Ventayen (2018) stated how the Department of Education (DepEd) integrate a deeper sense of technology in education under the K-12 implementation when they offer ICT track, and this includes Computer Systems Servicing (CSS) with trainings such as the National Certificate II (NCII). In addition, Villanueva (2015) generally give the concept of CSS as part of the educational journey of the students and serves as their field of specialization when they chose the Information Communication Technology (ICT) strand. Simos et al. (2022) pointed out the need to adapt the use of technology as a tool in education. Leburonetal (2009) emphasized the integration of ICT in education and Rogers (2003) stated its successful innovation in the educational field. Famor (2005) provided information on the importance of ICT in education which leads to a strong workforce.

On the other hand, the Philippine Star (2005) detailed the gap of knowledge and skills between the students and teachers when computer concepts are concerned. Moreover, Unwin (2005) discussed the condition of misplaced teachers and students in the educational landscape of the K-12 curriculum that becomes the problem in achieving mastery and skill development. Eurasia (2017) stated specific problems encountered by students in learning ICT-related courses like signal, computer malfunction, viruses, loafd shedding, and others; while Cajilin (2009) revealed the scarcity of teacher training that affect the process of instructional delivery.

With that, Lubian (2007) emphasized the role of teachers in shaping the future of the students; while Wighting (2006) stated how computers affect the learning experiences. On the other hand, Hassare (2006) provides an analysis on the strengths and weaknesses in pedagogies and technological use. Holzweiss et al. (2014) on their study shed enlightenment on the importance of curricula matching with industry expectations and that includes the ICT-related courses. This is seconded by Bates and Santere (2019) when they emphasized the importance of alignment of educational offerings and educational practices.

On the context of key dimensions of gap analysis, the study of Asan (2003) provided an in-depth understanding on how CSS provided a new knowledge on the part of students and teachers; while Oliquino (2019) pointed out the need for assessment of the 21st century skills which are utilized in the learning of CSS. McCormack et al. (2017) focused on the importance of communication dimensions particularly the way teachers, students, stakeholders should communicate with each other to contribute to the success of every program implementation; while Stern (2015) provides information on the problems of communication and how it affects the employment of a graduate student. Kincard and Elder (2005) emphasized the importance of conducive learning environment which is part of service quality.

Lastly, Balwati (2004) provided the importance of a systematic development program to implement changes which served as a key idea in the implementation of a program.

After analyzing the depths of information that the literature had provided, the researcher found dearth in the existing literature on the analysis of the gaps on the five key dimensions which were knowledge, communication, delivery, perception, and service quality being put in one model. Thus, an action plan utilizing a Pentapartite Gap Analysis model comprising of the said dimensions, became the output of this study. Moreover, the said output would improve the Computer System Servicing specialization at the three public Senior High Schools in District VI, Manila and could lead to a thorough and pertinent educational experience that equips students with the

changing demands of the computer system servicing field.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed quantitative descriptive research design which intended to create a snapshot of the current state of the study. This permitted and gave the researcher a relatively and complete information about the study being conducted to improve the questions for the further study (Stangor, 2011). This study described the current situation of the Computer Systems Servicing (CSS) implementation along with the utilization using the Pentapartite Gap Analysis which comprises of knowledge, communication, delivery, perception, and service quality.

Respondents

The respondents of the study comprised of teachers and students of the three schools in District VI Manila. The study was composed of 10 teachers and 30 students who were selected in two different sampling techniques: purposive sampling and random sampling technique.

Below is the distribution of respondents coming from the locale of the study:

<i>Locale of the Study</i>	<i>Teachers</i>	<i>Students</i>
Mariano Marcos Memorial High School	4	10
Elpidio Quirino High School	3	10
Eulogio "Amang" Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology Vocational High School	3	10
Total	10	30

The teachers were selected utilizing a purposive sampling technique in which they were the teachers with CSS specialization and were teaching the students taking up CSS track. On the other hand, the students were randomly selected as long as they were enrolled and taking up CSS as their senior high school track.

Instruments

The survey questionnaire was the research instrument used in gathering the data:

Survey Questionnaire. The researcher-made questionnaire was made and presented to the research adviser for comments and suggestions through the reading of related literature with similar ideas on the above variables centering on the assessment of "PENTAPARTITE GAP ANALYSIS: Improving the Computer System Servicing Specialization of Three Public Schools of Senior High School in District VI Manila". The researcher sought the guidance and assistance of the adviser in the formulation of the questionnaire. Here

Part I. Demographic Profile of the Respondents. This part elicited the respondents age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and number of years in service.

Part II. Assessment on the issues face by the respondents when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization. This generated data as to the issues do the respondents faced when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization.

Part III. Assessment on the respondents Perceptions towards the capability of their school in terms of school facilities, teachers and Instructional materials. This part contained the assessment of the teachers and students on "PENTAPARTITE GAP ANALYSIS: Improving the Computer System Servicing Specialization of Three Public Schools of Senior High School in District VI Manila".

The research questionnaire was meticulously designed to explore the nuances of the Computer System Servicing specialization within District VI schools. By incorporating Likert-scale questions ranged from 5 = Highly Extent, 4 = Extent, 3 = Moderately Extent, 2 = Least Extent and 1 = Very Least Extent, qualitative prompts, and a comprehensive coverage of the Penta partite Gap Analysis dimensions, the questionnaire gathered a rich dataset to inform the study's analysis and recommendations.

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument

Advisers and experts were consulted in the formulation of the instrument. There were several corrections and revisions made after every submission. The sample-made survey questionnaire was brought to a panel of experts for validation. Based on the recommendations of the validators, the survey questionnaire was revised to its appropriate final form to achieve the objectives of the study. The final form of the survey questionnaire was submitted again to the adviser for approval.

After the advisers' approval, the instrument was then set to be distributed. To test the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaire, it was pilot tested on to the teachers who were not part of the study.

Procedure

The chronological steps were undertaken by the researcher in order to gather data needed in the study:

1. Written permission was sought from the Schools Division Office in the City of Manila to allow the researcher to distribute and retrieve the survey questionnaire.
2. Upon approval of the written permission, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to the teachers and students in the schools in District VI in the City Manila.
3. The researcher retrieved research-made questionnaire; data were tabulated, analyzed, treated, and interpreted with the assistance of a statistician and the adviser.
4. The researcher sought the help of a statistician for the treatment and interpretation of data as well as the findings.
5. Statistical findings were presented in tabular form and described and interpreted by the researcher.
6. The thesis was drafted and encoded and readied for final oral defense.

Data Analysis

After all the questionnaires were retrieved, the responses were tallied and tabulated. The data were processed using the following statistical tools.

Frequency. This was utilized in the actual response to a specific item in the questionnaire where the respondents wrote their answers.

Weighted Mean. This was used to denote the average responses of the respondents. This was used to answer sub-problem number 1 and 2.

Likert Scale. The five-point Likert scale was utilized to describe the (a) the issues the respondents faced during the first implementation of the computer system servicing specialization; and (b) assessment of the teachers and student on pentapartite gap analysis namely knowledge, communication, delivery, perception, and service quality.

Ranking. This will be used to determine the order of decreasing or increasing magnitude of variations. The largest frequency is ranked number 1, 2, and so on down last rank and number.

T-Test. This was used to determine the significant difference between the responses of the teachers and student on the PENTAPARTITE GAP ANALYSIS: Improving the Computer System Servicing Specialization of Three Public Schools of Senior High School in District VI Manila.”

The critical t-value at five percent (0.05) level of significance (alpha level) with respective degrees of freedom was used to set the region of acceptance and rejection in the study.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers completed this study bearing in mind the ethical considerations especially in observing confidentiality, quality, and human subject protection. Permission was first sought from the office of the schools from District VI Manila where the researcher conducted the study. Written and informed consent was also secured from the respondents who are the students and teachers. Considering that certain respondents were still minors, the researcher explained their right to voluntarily withdraw from the study at any time, the central purpose of the study, the procedures used in the data collection, comments about protecting confidentiality, statement about known risks associated with, and the expected benefits to accrue by participating in the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the quantitative data gathered with the corresponding interpretation and analysis.

Sub-problem 1: What issues do the respondents face when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization in terms of:

School Facilities

Table 1 presented how the teachers and students as respondents generally rated the indicators on the issues face by the when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization in terms of facilities compositely as moderately encountered, where indicator 3 which stated, “There were any instances where technical malfunctions or limitations in the lab equipment hindered the effective delivery of computer system servicing instruction.” (WM = 4.07) rated encountered as rank no. 1; Indicator 2 “There are adequate physical space to impact the practical hands-on sessions and group activities required for the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 3.33) rated moderately encountered and ranked no. 2; Indicator 9, “The availability of specialized tools and diagnostic equipment influence the depth and quality of hands-on learning experiences in the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 3.28) rated moderately encountered and obtained rank no. 3; Indicator 6 which stated, “The condition and maintenance of lab facilities impact students' overall satisfaction and engagement with the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 3.00) rated moderately encountered as rank no. 4; Indicator 1 “There are any challenges related to the availability of dedicated computer labs or facilities equipped with the necessary hardware and software for the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 2.78) rated moderately encountered and ranked no. 5; Indicator 4 “The students face difficulties accessing and utilizing the required software tools or simulators due to limitations in the school's IT infrastructure for the specialization.” (WM = 2.70) rated moderately

encountered, ranked no. 6; Indicator 10, “There any financial constraints or limitations in securing the necessary resources for setting up and maintaining the lab facilities for the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 2.64) rated moderately encountered and ranked no. 7; Indicator 8 which stated, “There were any challenges in providing a safe and conducive learning environment in the lab facilities, considering factors such as electrical safety, ergonomics, and ventilation.” (WM = 2.53) rated moderately encountered ranked no. 8; Indicator 7, “The school provide sufficient technical support and maintenance for lab equipment or were there instances where equipment breakdowns caused disruptions in teaching and learning.” (WM = 2.20) rated least encountered and ranked no. 9, and lastly, indicator 5 “There were any issues related to scheduling conflicts or resource allocation for the computer system servicing specialization labs that affected students' learning experiences.” (WM = 2.14) rated least encountered as rank no. 10, respectively.

Table 1. *Assessment of School Facilities*

Indicators	Teacher		Student		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. There are any challenges related to the availability of dedicated computer labs or facilities equipped with the necessary hardware and software for the computer system servicing specialization.	4.55	HE	1.00	VLE	2.78	ME	5
2. There are adequate physical space to impact the practical hands-on sessions and group activities required for the computer system servicing specialization.	4.06	E	2.60	VLE	3.33	ME	2
3. There were any instances where technical malfunctions or limitations in the lab equipment hindered the effective delivery of computer system servicing instruction.	4.13	E	1.00	VLE	4.07	E	1
4. The students face difficulties accessing and utilizing the required software tools or simulators due to limitations in the school's IT infrastructure for the specialization.	4.40	HE	1.00	VLE	2.70	ME	6
5. There were any issues related to scheduling conflicts or resource allocation for the computer system servicing specialization labs that affected students' learning experiences.	3.28	ME	1.00	VLE	2.14	LE	10
6. The condition and maintenance of lab facilities impact students' overall satisfaction and engagement with the computer system servicing specialization.	4.13	E	1.86	LE	3.00	ME	4
7. The school provides sufficient technical support and maintenance for lab equipment or there were instances where equipment breakdowns caused disruptions in teaching and learning.	3.40	E	1.00	VLE	2.20	LE	9
8. There were any challenges in providing a safe and conducive learning environment in the lab facilities, considering factors such as electrical safety, ergonomics, and ventilation.	4.06	E	1.00	VLE	2.53	LE	8
9. The availability of specialized tools and diagnostic equipment influence the depth and quality of hands-on learning experiences in the computer system servicing specialization.	4.02	E	2.38	LE	3.20	ME	3
10. There any financial constraints or limitations in securing the necessary resources for setting up and maintaining the lab facilities for the computer system servicing specialization.	4.27	HE	1.00	VLE	2.64	ME	7
Overall Weighted Mean	4.03	E	1.38	VLE	2.71	ME	

The composite weighted mean score of 2.71, which suggested that both teacher and students perceived the issues faced by the school when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization in terms of facilities to be moderately encountered, shed light on the challenges the institution has navigated during the initial stages of program implementation. While this score indicated that the issues were not overwhelmingly severe, it also underscored the importance of addressing facility-related concerns to ensure the optimal learning environment for students pursuing this specialization. These issues could encompass factors such as insufficient equipment, limited laboratory pace, or inadequate infrastructure for practical training, all of which could impact the quality of education and the overall student experience.

Moreover, this rating served as a valuable starting point for the school to initiate targeted improvements and enhancements in its facilities. Recognizing that these challenges were moderately encountered suggested that there is room for growth and development. By addressing these issues and investing in upgraded facilities, the school can create a more conducive and modern learning environment, ultimately providing students with a better educational experience. It also signified the institution's commitment to adapt and improve as it continues to offer computer system servicing as a specialization, which can potentially attract more students and bolster its reputation in the long run.

Teachers

Table 2. *Assessment of Teachers*

Indicators	Teacher		Student		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	

1. The teachers encounter challenges in recruiting qualified and experienced instructors who possess a strong background in computer system servicing for the specialization.	3.48	E	1.00	VLE	2.24	LE	5
2. The shortage of skilled teachers in computer system servicing impact the breadth and depth of topics covered in the initial stages of specialization implementation.	5.00	HE	1.00	VLE	3.00	ME	2
3. There are any issues related to aligning the teaching methodologies of newly hired instructors with the hands-on and practical nature of the computer system servicing specialization.	4.00	E	1.00	VLE	2.50	LE	4
4. The teachers' lack of familiarity with industry trends and emerging technologies among teachers pose challenges in providing up-to-date instruction within the computer system servicing specialization.	3.38	ME	1.00	VLE	2.19	LE	6.5
5. There were difficulties in balancing theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the curriculum due to variances in instructors' expertise within the computer system servicing specialization.	3.19	ME	1.00	VLE	2.10	LE	9
6. Integrations of industry professionals or guest lecturers into the teaching team influence the quality and relevance of instruction for the computer system servicing specialization.	4.14	E	2.60	ME	3.37	ME	1
7. There are any communication gaps or misalignments between teachers and students in terms of expectations, course content, or assessment methods for the computer system servicing specialization.	4.39	HE	1.00	VLE	2.70	ME	3
8. The recruitment of part-time or adjunct instructors affect the consistency and coherence of instruction within the computer system servicing specialization.	3.37	ME	1.00	VLE	2.19	LE	6.5
9. The orientation and training of new instructors impact their ability to effectively deliver engaging and comprehensive lessons for the computer system servicing specialization.	3.20	ME	1.00	VLE	2.10	LE	9
10. There are many challenges in fostering a collaborative and supportive teaching environment among instructors when implementing the computer system servicing specialization.	3.20	ME	1.00	VLE	2.10	LE	9
Overall weighted mean	3.74	E	1.16	VLE	2.45	LE	

As exhibited in Table 2, the teachers and students respondents generally rated the indicators on the issues face by the teachers themselves and the students on their teacher when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization as least encountered, indicator 6 “Integrations of industry professionals or guest lecturers into the teaching team influence the quality and relevance of instruction for the computer system servicing specialization” (WM = 3.37) rated moderately encountered as rank no. 1; indicator 2 which stated, “The shortage of skilled teachers in computer system servicing impact the breadth and depth of topics covered in the initial stages of specialization implementation.” (WM = 3.00) rated moderately encountered as rank no. 2; indicator 7 “There are any communication gaps or misalignments between teachers and students in terms of expectations, course content, or assessment methods for the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 2.70) rated moderately encountered as rank no. 3; indicator 3, “There are any issues related to aligning the teaching methodologies of newly hired instructors with the hands-on and practical nature of the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 2.50) rated least encountered as rank no. 4; indicator 1 stated as “The teachers encounter challenges in recruiting qualified and experienced instructors who possess a strong background in computer system servicing for the specialization.” (WM = 2.24) rated least encountered as rank no. 5; indicators 4 and 8 “The teachers' lack of familiarity with industry trends and emerging technologies among teachers pose challenges in providing up-to-date instruction within the computer system servicing specialization;” and “The recruitment of part-time or adjunct instructors affect the consistency and coherence of instruction within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 2.19) both rated least encountered as rank no. 6.5; and lastly, indicators 5, 9, and 10 which respectively stated, “There were difficulties in balancing theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the curriculum due to variances in instructors' expertise within the computer system servicing specialization;” “The orientation and training of new instructors impact their ability to effectively deliver engaging and comprehensive lessons for the computer system servicing specialization;” and “There are many challenges in fostering a collaborative and supportive teaching environment among instructors when implementing the computer system servicing specialization?” (WM = 2.10) rated least encountered as rank no. 10, respectively.

The overall composite weighted mean of 2.45, indicating that both teacher and students perceived the issues faced by the school when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization in terms of teachers to be least encountered, was an encouraging finding. It suggested that the institution effectively managed the challenges related to teacher availability and competence during the initial stages of program implementation. Having highly qualified and skilled educators was paramount in ensuring the quality of education, especially in a specialized field like computer system servicing. The fact that these issues were perceived as least encountered by both groups implied that the school made a concerted effort to employ capable faculty members who could deliver the necessary knowledge and guidance to students pursuing this specialization.

Also, this positive assessment regarding the availability and competence of teachers reflected the school's commitment to investing in its human resources, a critical factor in the success of any educational program. It also underscored the institution's dedication to

ensuring that students receive top-notch instruction, setting a solid foundation for their academic and professional growth in the field of computer system servicing. While it was essential to address any remaining issues, this positive perception can boost the school's reputation and make it an attractive choice for students interested in this specialization. It also highlighted the importance of ongoing professional development and support for faculty to maintain and enhance the quality of education provided.

Instructional Materials

Table 3. *Assessment of Instructional Materials*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Student</i>		<i>Composite</i>		Rank
		<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	
1.	There are challenges in sourcing or creating relevant and up-to-date instructional materials, such as textbooks, online resources, and practical guides, for the computer system servicing specialization.	4.33	HE	1.80	VLE	3.07	ME	6
2.	The availability of comprehensive and cohesive course materials impact students' ability to grasp the essential concepts and skills in the early stages of the specialization.	4.34	HE	3.48	E	3.91	E	5
3.	There are any difficulties in aligning the instructional materials with the specific learning outcomes and industry standards of the computer system servicing specialization.	4.29	HE	1.00	VLE	2.65	ME	8
4.	The lack of interactive or multimedia resources hinder the engagement and practical understanding of complex computer system servicing topics within the curriculum.	4.19	E	1.00	VLE	2.60	ME	9
5.	The integration of case studies, real-world scenarios, and practical examples in instructional materials enhances students' problem-solving skills and real-world application capabilities.	4.14	E	5.00	HE	4.57	HE	1
6.	There are any issues with the accessibility of online materials or the compatibility of digital resources with students' devices for the computer system servicing specialization.	3.50	E	1.00	VLE	2.25	LE	10
7.	The students face challenges in obtaining required materials, either due to unavailability or financial constraints, impacting their ability to fully engage with the specialization content.	4.36	HE	1.00	VLE	2.68	ME	7
8.	There are concerns about the balance between theoretical content and practical exercises within the instructional materials for the computer system servicing specialization.	4.12	E	4.00	E	4.06	E	4
9.	The early implementation stages impact the continuous refinement and expansion of the range of instructional materials available for the computer system servicing specialization.	4.14	E	4.00	E	4.07	E	3
10.	There any collaborations with industry partners, publishers, or experts to address the gaps in instructional materials and ensure alignment with the evolving needs of the computer system servicing field.	3.40	E	5.00	HE	4.20	HE	2
Overall weighted mean		4.08	E	2.73	ME	3.41	E	

As portrayed in Table 3, the teachers and students as respondents generally rated the indicators on the issues faced by them when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization in terms of instructional materials as encountered, making indicator 5 “The integration of case studies, real-world scenarios, and practical examples in instructional materials enhances students' problem-solving skills and real-world application capabilities.” (WM = 4.57) rated highly encountered as rank no. 1; indicator 10 “There any collaborations with industry partners, publishers, or experts to address the gaps in instructional materials and ensure alignment with the evolving needs of the computer system servicing field.” (WM = 4.20) rated highly encountered and ranked no. 2; indicator 9, “The early implementation stages impact the continuous refinement and expansion of the range of instructional materials available for the computer system servicing specialization” (WM = 4.07) rated encountered as rank no. 3; indicator 8 “There are concerns about the balance between theoretical content and practical exercises within the instructional materials for the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.06) rated encountered as rank no. 4; indicator 2 “The availability of comprehensive and cohesive course materials impact students' ability to grasp the essential concepts and skills in the early stages of the specialization?” (WM = 3.91) rated encountered as rank no. 5; Indicator 1 “There are challenges in sourcing or creating relevant and up-to-date instructional materials, such as textbooks, online resources, and practical guides, for the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 3.07) both rated moderately encountered as rank no. 6; Indicator 7 which stated as “The students face challenges in obtaining required materials, either due to unavailability or financial constraints, impacting their ability to fully engage with the specialization content” (WM = 2.68) both rated moderately encountered as rank no. 7; Indicator 3 “There are any difficulties in aligning the instructional materials with the specific learning outcomes and industry standards of the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 3.07) rated moderately encountered as rank no. 8; Indicator 4 “The lack of interactive or multimedia resources hinder the engagement and practical understanding of complex computer system servicing topics within the curriculum.” (WM = 2.60) both rated moderately encountered as rank no. 9; and lastly, indicator 6 “There are any issues with the accessibility of online materials or the compatibility of digital resources with students' devices for the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 2.25) rated least encountered as rank no.

10, respectively.

The composite weighted mean of 3.41, indicating that both teacher and students perceived the issues faced by the school when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization in terms of instructional materials to be encountered, shed light on a critical aspect of program development. Instructional materials played a pivotal role in delivering effective education, especially in technical fields like computer system servicing. This score suggested that the school did encounter challenges related to the availability or adequacy of instructional materials during the initial stages of program implementation. These challenges might include outdated textbooks, limited access to digital resources, or a lack of specialized materials required for practical training. Recognizing these challenges was the first step toward improvement, as it highlighted the need for investment in up-to-date and relevant instructional materials to enhance the overall quality of education.

Addressing these challenges in instructional materials was essential for the continued success and competitiveness of the computer system servicing specialization. Modern and comprehensive materials not only enrich the learning experience but also ensured that students were well-prepared to meet the demands of the rapidly evolving technology industry. This score served as a valuable indicator for the school to prioritize investments in resources and materials, demonstrating a commitment to providing a cutting-edge education in computer system servicing. Additionally, by addressing these challenges, the school could potentially attract more students who sought access to high-quality instructional materials, contributing to the growth and reputation of the program and institution.

Table 4. *Summary of Respondents' Assessment on the Issues Face when First Implementing the Computer System Servicing Specialization*

Indicators	Teacher		Student		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. School Facilities	4.03	E	1.38	VLE	2.71	ME	2
2. Teachers	3.74	E	1.16	VLE	2.45	LE	3
3. Instructional Materials	4.08	E	2.73	ME	3.41	E	1
Overall weighted mean	3.95	E	1.76	VLE	2.86	ME	

Table 4 illustrated the summary of assessment of teachers and students as respondents on the issues face when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization. It could be seen by the data that the teachers rated all indicators which were school facilities, teachers, and instructional materials as encountered as appeared by their respective weighted mean of 4.03, 3.74, and 4.08. Thus, yielded an overall of weighted mean of 3.95 and was verbally interpreted as encountered.

The student respondents rated “instructional materials as moderately encountered with a weighted mean of 2.73. except that they rated “school facilities” and “teachers” as least encountered with their respective weighted mean of 1.38 and 1.16. Hence, yielded an overall weighted mean of 1.76 and verbally interpreted as very least encountered.

As a whole, the teachers and students respondents rated the indicators on the issues face when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization as moderately encountered, “instructional materials” (WM = 3.41) rated encountered as rank no. 1; “school facilities” (WM = 2.71) rated moderately encountered as rank no. 2, and lastly, “teachers” (WM = 2.45) rated least encountered as rank no. 3, respectively.

The overall composite weighted mean of 2.86, signified that both teacher and students perceived the issues faced by the school when first implementing the computer system servicing specialization in terms of facilities, teachers, and instructional materials to be moderately encountered, presented a balanced perspective on the challenges encountered during the initial stages of program implementation. This indicated that the institution was confronted with a reasonable degree of difficulties in these crucial areas. While the challenges may not have been extreme, they still warranted attention and improvement to ensure the highest quality of education. It was important to recognize that these three aspects—facilities, teachers, and instructional materials—interacted closely and collectively influenced the overall educational experience. Therefore, addressing these issues comprehensively would likely lead to significant enhancements in the program's quality.

This moderate rating served as a valuable starting point for the school to initiate targeted improvements in these critical areas. It highlighted the need for investments in facilities, recruitment and professional development of teachers, and the acquisition of up-to-date instructional materials. Addressing these challenges systematically would lead to a more conducive and modern learning environment, better-equipped faculty, and enriched course materials, ultimately providing students with a more robust and comprehensive educational experience. It also underscored the school's commitment to adapt and improve continually as it continued to offer computer system servicing as a specialization, which could contribute to its long-term success and reputation in the field.

Subproblem No. 2. To what extent is the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization based on the assessment of teachers and students in terms of the following:

Knowledge

Table 5. *Assessment of Knowledge*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Student</i>		<i>Composite</i>		Rank
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	
1. It describes the depth of theoretical knowledge covered in the computer system servicing specialization curriculum.	4.50	TVGE	4.53	TVGE	4.52	TVGE	1
2. Are the instructors well-versed in advanced topics such as virtualization, cloud computing, and advanced troubleshooting techniques?	3.60	TGE	4.22	TVGE	3.91	TGE	9
3. The course materials incorporate the latest advancements in computer hardware and software technologies.	4.00	TGE	4.33	TVGE	4.17	TGE	6
4. Does the curriculum bridge the gap between foundational concepts and advanced technical knowledge required for computer system servicing?	4.00	TGE	4.22	TVGE	4.11	TGE	8
5. Students are exposed to real-world case studies and scenarios to enhance their practical understanding of computer system servicing.	4.50	TVGE	4.20	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	2
6. The curriculum emphasizes the importance of keeping up with evolving cybersecurity threats and protective measures.	4.20	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	4.28	TVGE	4
7. The specialization covers emerging trends like Internet of Things (IoT) device management and integration.	4.00	TGE	4.46	TVGE	4.23	TVGE	5
8. Does the curriculum address the intricacies of operating system optimization and customization for various purposes?	3.50	TGE	4.16	TGE	3.83	TGE	10
9. Students are provided with opportunities to engage in hands-on labs that simulate complex computer system troubleshooting and maintenance tasks.	4.30	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	4.31	TVGE	3
10. The specialization curriculum encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills by incorporating complex hardware and software integration challenges.	3.90	TGE	4.35	TVGE	4.13	TGE	7
Overall weighted mean	4.05	TGE	4.32	TVGE	4.18	TGE	

As indicated in Table 5, the teacher respondents rated the four indicators on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of knowledge as to a very great extent as shown by their perspective weighted mean of 4.50, 4.50, 4.20, and 4.30. The rest of the indicators rated to a great extent, as evidenced by their weighted mean of 3.60, 4.00, 4.00, 3.50, and 3.90. Thus, yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.05 and was verbally interpreted as to a great extent.

However, the student respondents rated nine of the indicators as to a very great extent as demonstrated by their weighted mean of 4.53, 4.22, 4.33, 4.22, 4.20, 4.35, 4.46, 4.35, and 4.35. Only indicator 8 rated to a great extent with a weighted mean of 4.16. Hence, it yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.31 and was interpreted as to a very great extent.

Generally, the teacher and student respondent rated the indicators in on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of knowledge as to a great extent, indicator 1 “It describes the depth of theoretical knowledge covered in the computer system servicing specialization curriculum.” (WM = 4.52) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 1; indicator 5 “Students are exposed to real-world case studies and scenarios to enhance their practical understanding of computer system servicing.” (WM = 4.35) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 2; indicator 9 “Students are provided with opportunities to engage in hands-on labs that simulate complex computer system troubleshooting and maintenance tasks” (WM = 4.31) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 3; indicator 6 “The curriculum emphasizes the importance of keeping up with evolving cybersecurity threats and protective measures.” (WM = 4.28) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 4; indicator 7 “The specialization covers emerging trends like Internet of Things (IoT) device management and integration” (WM = 4.23) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 5; indicator 3 “The course materials incorporate the latest advancements in computer hardware and software technologies.” (WM = 4.17) rated to a great extent as rank no. 6; indicator 10 “The specialization curriculum encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills by incorporating complex hardware and software integration challenges.” (WM = 4.13) rated to a great extent as rank no. 7; indicator 4 “Does the curriculum bridge the gap between foundational concepts and advanced technical knowledge required for computer system servicing?” (WM = 4.11) rated to a great extent as rank no. 8; indicator 2 “Are the instructors well-versed in advanced topics such as virtualization, cloud computing, and advanced troubleshooting techniques?” (WM = 3.91) rated to a great extent as rank no. 9, and lastly, indicator 8 “Does the curriculum address the intricacies of operating system optimization and customization for various purposes?” (WM = 3.83) rated to a great extent as rank no. 10, respectively.

Hence, the findings of this study underscored the remarkable alignment between teacher and student respondents in their evaluation of the school's capability in offering computer system servicing as a specialization. The resounding agreement, with both groups rating the indicators to a great extent, as reflected by the impressive overall weighted mean of 4.18, signified a strong consensus on the school's competence in this domain. This robust convergence of opinions between teacher and students not only highlighted the school's commitment to delivering high-quality education in computer system servicing but also suggested an effective communication and transparency between the two key stakeholders. It indicated that the institution's curriculum, faculty, and resources were adequately

equipping students with the knowledge and skills required to excel in this specialized field, setting a solid foundation for their future careers in computer system servicing.

Furthermore, the high rating given by both teachers and students spoke to the effectiveness of the school's educational program and underscores the institution's dedication to staying current with the evolving demands of the technology industry. This impressive consensus bodes well for the prospects of students specializing in computer system servicing, as they were likely to be well-prepared and competitive in the job market upon graduation. Overall, the findings not only validated the school's reputation in this specialized field but also served as a testament to its commitment to providing a high-quality educational experience that aligned with the expectations and aspirations of its students and the broader technology sector.

The result was in consonance with what Lubian (2007) stated that the teachers touch the future of the learner. For a better integration of ICT into the Philippine education system to improve the quality of learning and none the computer skills of young Filipinos. Teachers teach well for the students to learn.

Delivery

Table 6. *Assessment of Delivery*

Indicators	Teacher		Student		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. The school integrate practical hands-on sessions into the computer system servicing specialization to reinforce theoretical concepts.	4.39	TVGE	4.54	TVGE	4.47	TVGE	1
2. There regular workshops, seminars, or guest lectures conducted by industry professionals to provide real-world insights to students.	3.20	TME	4.22	TVGE	3.71	TGE	10
3. The instructors employ a variety of teaching methods, such as multimedia presentations, interactive discussions, and collaborative projects, to cater to diverse learning styles.	4.20	TVGE	4.20	TVGE	4.20	TVGE	2
4. The school utilize simulation software and virtual labs to replicate real-world computer system servicing scenarios.	3.40	TGE	4.36	TVGE	3.88	TGE	9
5. The students are given opportunities to work on team projects that simulate complex system servicing tasks, fostering collaboration and problem-solving skills.	4.00	TGE	4.34	TVGE	4.17	TGE	3
6. The school offer flexible learning options, such as online courses or evening classes, to accommodate students with different schedules.	3.89	TGE	4.40	TVGE	4.15	TGE	5
7. The school offer practical internships or work placements for students to apply their computer system servicing skills in real-world settings.	3.78	TGE	4.24	TVGE	4.01	TGE	8
8. The curriculum incorporates mock certification exams to prepare students for industry-standard certifications in computer system servicing.	4.00	TGE	4.05	TGE	4.03	TGE	7
9. There mechanisms in place to gather regular feedback from students to improve the delivery of the computer system servicing specialization.	4.00	TGE	4.32	TVGE	4.16	TGE	4
10. The school provides individualized guidance and mentorship to students who may require additional support in understanding complex concepts related to computer system servicing.	3.97	TGE	4.27	TVGE	4.13	TGE	6
Overall weighted mean	3.88	TGE	4.29	TVGE	4.09	TGE	

As manifested in Table 6, the teacher respondents rated the two indicators on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of delivery as to a very great extent as shown by the weighted mean of 4.39 and 4.20. Indicators 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 rated to a great extent as shown by their weighted mean of 3.40, 4.00, 3.89, 3.78, 4.00, 4.00, and 3.97. However, indicator 2 rated to a moderate extent with a weighted mean of 3.20. These values obtained yielded an overall weighted mean of 3.88 and was verbally interpreted as “to a great extent.”

Meanwhile, the student respondents rated nine of the indicators as to a very great extent as demonstrated by their weighted mean of 4.54, 4.22, 4.20, 4.36, 4.34, 4.40, 4.24, 4.32, and 4.27. Indicator 8 rated “to a great extent” with a weighted mean of 4.15. Hence, yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.29 and was interpreted as to a very great extent.

As a whole, the teachers and students respondents rated the indicators on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of delivery as to a great extent; indicator 1 “The school integrate practical hands-on sessions into the computer system servicing specialization to reinforce theoretical concepts” (WM = 4.47) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 1; indicator 3 “The instructors employ a variety of teaching methods, such as multimedia presentations, interactive discussions, and collaborative projects, to cater to diverse learning styles.” (WM = 4.20) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 2;

indicator 5, “The students are given opportunities to work on team projects that simulate complex system servicing tasks, fostering collaboration and problem-solving skills.” (WM = 4.17) rated to a great extent as rank no. 3; indicator 9 “There mechanisms in place to gather regular feedback from students to improve the delivery of the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.16) rated to a great extent as rank no. 4; indicator 6 “The school offer flexible learning options, such as online courses or evening classes, to accommodate students with different schedules.” (WM = 4.15) rated to a great extent as rank no. 5; indicator 10 “The school provides individualized guidance and mentorship to students who may require additional support in understanding complex concepts related to computer system servicing.” (WM = 4.13) rated to a great extent as rank no. 6; indicator 8 “The curriculum incorporates mock certification exams to prepare students for industry-standard certifications in computer system servicing.” (WM = 4.03) rated to a great extent as rank no. 7; indicator 7 that stated, “The school offer practical internships or work placements for students to apply their computer system servicing skills in real-world settings.” (WM = 4.01) rated to a great extent as rank no. 8; indicator 4 “The school utilize simulation software and virtual labs to replicate real-world computer system servicing scenarios.” (WM = 3.88) rated to a great extent as rank no. 9, and lastly, indicator 2 “There regular workshops, seminars, or guest lectures conducted by industry professionals to provide real-world insights to students.” (WM = 3.71) rated to a great extent as rank no. 10, respectively.

Moreover, the remarkable consensus between teacher and student respondents, both rating the school's capability in offering computer system servicing as a specialization to a great extent, as evidence by the impressive overall composite weighted mean of 4.09, underscored the institution's strong commitment to excellence in program delivery. This congruence of perspectives suggested a well-coordinated and effective educational ecosystem where faculty, curriculum, and resources align seamlessly to provide students with a comprehensive and enriching learning experience. Such alignment was vital for the success of students pursuing computer system servicing as it not only ensured they received a high-quality education but also prepared them to meet the evolving demands of the technology industry, making them competitive in their future careers.

Moreover, the consistently high rating from both teachers and students signaled a strong sense of mutual understanding and satisfaction within the institution. It implied that the school was not only meeting but exceeding the expectations of its stakeholders, fostering an environment of trust and collaboration. This positive feedback reaffirmed the institution's position as a leader in the field of computer system servicing education, and it was likely to attract more students seeking to specialize in this area. Overall, the study's findings reflected a harmonious relationship between the school and its students, with a shared commitment to delivering excellence in computer system servicing education, which was essential for the continued success and growth of both parties.

Communication

As shown in Table 7, the teachers rated the three indicators on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of communication as to a very great extent as shown by the weighted mean of 5.00, 4.28 and 4.38. Indicators 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, and 10 rated to a great extent as shown by their weighted mean of 4.14, 4.07, 4.15, 4.06, and 4.11. Meanwhile, indicators 6 and 7 rated to a moderate extent with a weighted mean of 3.00 and yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.02 and verbally interpreted as to a great extent.

The student respondents, on the other hand, rated six of the indicators as to a very great extent as demonstrated by their weighted mean of 4.35, 4.35, 4.27, 4.22, 4.26, and 4.22. The rest of the indicators rated to a great extent with a weighted mean of 4.00 and yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.16 and was interpreted as to a great extent.

Furthermore, the teacher and student respondents rated the indicators on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of communications as to a great extent, indicator 1 “There is a clear and accessible communication of course objectives, expectations, and assessment criteria to students enrolled in the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.68) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 1; indicator 9 “The students are encouraged to collaborate and communicate with each other to solve problems and share insights related to computer system servicing tasks.” (WM = 4.30) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 2; indicator 2 “Students are provided with a well-defined communication channel to reach out to instructors for questions, clarifications, and support regarding course materials and assignments.” (WM = 4.27) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 3; indicator 4 “Students are well informed about changes or updates to the course schedule, content, or assessments on time.” (WM = 4.19) rated to a great extent as rank no. 4; indicator 3 “The school use online platforms, forums, or email to facilitate discussions and information sharing among students within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.17) rated to a great extent as rank no. 5; indicator 5 “The school provide regular feedback to students on their progress, assignments, and practical projects within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.14) rated to a great extent as rank no. 6; indicator 10 “The school fosters communication skills in students by integrating group presentations, technical writing assignments, or mock client interactions within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.06) rated to a great extent as rank no. 7; indicator 8 “The school leverage multimedia resources effectively, such as video tutorials and visual aids, to enhance communication of complex technical concepts in the specialization.” (WM = 4.03) rated to a great extent as rank no. 8; indicator 7 “Are there dedicated communication channels or events that connect students in the computer system servicing specialization with alumni or industry professionals for networking and mentorship opportunities?” (WM = 3.62) rated to a great extent as rank no. 9, and lastly, indicator 6 “The school encourage open communication and active participation during lectures, seminars, and hands-on sessions for the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 3.50) rated to a great extent as rank no. 10, respectively.

Table 7. Assessment of Communication

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Student</i>		<i>Composite</i>		Rank
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	
1. There is a clear and accessible communication of course objectives, expectations, and assessment criteria to students enrolled in the computer system servicing specialization.	5.00	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	4.68	TVGE	1
2. Students are provided with a well-defined communication channel to reach out to instructors for questions, clarifications, and support regarding course materials and assignments.	4.14	TGE	4.35	TVGE	4.27	TVGE	3
3. The school use online platforms, forums, or email to facilitate discussions and information sharing among students within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.07	TGE	4.27	TVGE	4.17	TGE	5
4. Students are well informed about changes or updates to the course schedule, content, or assessments on time.	4.15	TGE	4.22	TVGE	4.19	TGE	4
5. The school provide regular feedback to students on their progress, assignments, and practical projects within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.28	TVGE	4.00	TGE	4.14	TGE	6
6. The school encourage open communication and active participation during lectures, seminars, and hands-on sessions for the computer system servicing specialization.	3.00	TME	4.00	TGE	3.50	TGE	10
7. Are there dedicated communication channels or events that connect students in the computer system servicing specialization with alumni or industry professionals for networking and mentorship opportunities?	3.00	TME	4.26	TVGE	3.62	TGE	9
8. The school leverage multimedia resources effectively, such as video tutorials and visual aids, to enhance communication of complex technical concepts in the specialization.	4.06	TGE	4.00	TGE	4.03	TGE	8
9. The students are encouraged to collaborate and communicate with each other to solve problems and share insights related to computer system servicing tasks.	4.38	TVGE	4.22	TVGE	4.30	TVGE	2
10. The school fosters communication skills in students by integrating group presentations, technical writing assignments, or mock client interactions within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.11	TGE	4.00	TGE	4.06	TGE	7
Overall weighted mean	4.02	TGE	4.17	TGE	4.10	TGE	

Also, the remarkable consensus among both teacher and student respondents, who rated the school's capability in offering computer system servicing as a specialization to a great extent in terms of communication, as demonstrated by the overall composite weighted mean of 4.09, underscored the institution's prowess in fostering effective communication channels. This congruence in ratings highlighted the school's dedication to transparent and efficient communication between all stakeholders, creating an environment where vital information flows seamlessly. Such open lines of communication not only facilitated a smooth learning process but also contributed to the overall success of students specializing in computer system servicing, as they can readily access support, resources, and guidance, ultimately enhancing their educational journey.

Moreover, this positive feedback from both teachers and students signified a shared commitment to maintaining an atmosphere of collaboration and cooperation within the institution. It reflected a mutual understanding and satisfaction with the communication systems in place, which is crucial for the holistic development of students. As the school continued to excel in this aspect, it was likely to attract more aspiring students seeking to specialize in computer system servicing, knowing they would be part of an educational community that valued effective communication as a cornerstone of their success. In conclusion, the findings not only validated the school's strength in communication but also underscored its dedication to providing a nurturing and supportive environment for all those engaged in the pursuit of computer system servicing education.

As reflected in Table 4, the teacher respondents rated the three indicators on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of perceptions as to a very great extent as manifested by the weighted mean of 4.37, 4.28 and 4.46. Indicators 4, 5, 6, 9, and 10 rated to a great extent as backed up by their weighted mean of 4.00, 4.00, 3.40, 4.17 and 4.03. Two indicators were rated to a moderate extent with a weighted mean of 3.38 and 3.27 and yielded an overall weighted mean of 3.94 and verbally interpreted as to a great extent.

On the part of the student respondents, they rated eight of the indicators as to a great extent as expressed by their weighted mean of 4.15, 4.12, 4.00, 4.10, 4.14, 4.16, 4.16, and 4.19. Indicator 1 were rated as to a very great extent with a weighted mean of 4.43 and only indicator 10 were rated to a moderate extent with a weighted mean of 3.28 and accumulated an overall weighted mean of 4.04 and was interpreted as to a great extent.

Perception

Table 8. *Assessment of Perception*

Indicators	Teacher		Student		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. The computer system servicing specialization perceived by students as a valuable and relevant area of study in the current technology landscape.	4.37	TVGE	4.43	TVGE	4.40	TVGE	1
2. The general perception among students about the availability of up-to-date resources, including textbooks, online materials, and hands-on equipment, for the specialization.	3.38	TME	4.15	TGE	3.77	TGE	7.5
3. The students perceive the overall quality of instruction and guidance provided by faculty members within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.28	TVGE	4.12	TGE	4.20	TVGE	3
4. The computer system servicing specialization perceived as competitive and aligned with industry demands by potential employers and hiring managers.	4.00	TGE	4.00	TGE	4.00	TGE	6
5. The reputation of the school's computer system servicing graduates in the industry in terms of their skills, knowledge, and preparedness for real-world challenges.	4.00	TGE	4.10	TGE	4.05	TGE	5
6. The computer system servicing specialization integrates feedback from industry professionals, alumni, and students to adapt to evolving industry needs.	3.40	TGE	4.14	TGE	3.77	TGE	7.5
7. The students and instructors perceive a sense of community and collaboration within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.46	TVGE	4.16	TGE	4.31	TVGE	2
8. The school communicate success stories, achievements, and innovative projects within the computer system servicing specialization to external stakeholders.	3.27	TME	4.16	TGE	3.70	TGE	9
9. The perceptions of students and faculty members regarding the school's efforts in fostering diversity and inclusivity within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.17	TGE	4.19	TGE	4.18	TGE	4
10. The computer system servicing specialization compare in perception to similar specializations offered by other institutions, both regionally and nationally.	4.03	TGE	3.28	TME	3.66	TGE	10
Overall weighted mean	3.94	TGE	4.08	TGE	4.01	TGE	

Collectively, the teacher and student respondents rated the indicators in on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of perceptions as to a great extent, indicator 1 “The computer system servicing specialization perceived by students as a valuable and relevant area of study in the current technology landscape.” (WM = 4.40) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 1; indicator 7 “The students and instructors perceive a sense of community and collaboration within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.31) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 2; indicator 3 “The students perceive the overall quality of instruction and guidance provided by faculty members within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.20) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 3; indicator 9 “The perceptions of students and faculty members regarding the school's efforts in fostering diversity and inclusivity within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.18) rated to a great extent as rank no. 4; indicator 5 “The reputation of the school's computer system servicing graduates in the industry in terms of their skills, knowledge, and preparedness for real-world challenges.” (WM = 4.05) rated to a great extent as rank no. 5; indicator 4 “The computer system servicing specialization perceived as competitive and aligned with industry demands by potential employers and hiring managers.” (WM = 4.00) rated to a great extent as rank no. 6; indicators 2 and 6 “The general perception among students about the availability of up-to-date resources, including textbooks, online materials, and hands-on equipment, for the specialization” and “The computer system servicing specialization integrates feedback from industry professionals, alumni, and students to adapt to evolving industry needs?” (WM = 3.77) rated to a great extent as rank no. 7.5; indicator 8 “The school communicate success stories, achievements, and innovative projects within the computer system servicing specialization to external stakeholders.” (WM = 3.70) rated to a great extent as rank no. 9, and lastly, indicator 10 “The computer system servicing specialization compare in perception to similar specializations offered by other institutions, both regionally and nationally.” (WM = 3.66) rated to a great extent as rank no. 10, respectively.

In conclusion, the convergence of opinions between teacher and student respondents, with both groups rating the school's capability in offering computer system servicing as a specialization to a great extent in terms of perceptions, as evidenced by the overall composite weighted mean of 4.01, underscored the institution's positive image and reputation in this field. This shared perception of the school's strengths in computer system servicing education spoke to its consistent efforts in maintaining a favorable learning environment and fostering a sense of trust and confidence among its stakeholders. Such alignment of perceptions not only enhanced the school's attractiveness to prospective students but also reinforced the commitment of current students to their educational journey, as they saw the institution as a credible and dependable source of knowledge and skills in computer system servicing.

Moreover, this study's findings suggested that the school has successfully cultivated a culture of excellence and credibility, as reflected

in the high rating for perceptions from both teacher and students. This positive atmosphere was conducive to learning and personal development, as it motivated students to strive for excellence and ensured that they were proud to be associated with the institution. As the school continued to maintain and build upon this positive perception, it was likely to remain a preferred choice for students interested in specializing in computer system servicing. In summary, the results affirmed the institution's strong position in the field and its commitment to providing a reputable and supportive environment for all those pursuing computer system servicing education.

The result agreed to what Lewis (2002) stated that the reason for using the computer vary from person since some of the computers in business are the one to perform accuracy, to be as productivity, to decrease bottle necks or hassles to simplify elevate one's status.

Service Quality

Table 9. *Assessment of Service Quality*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Student</i>		<i>Composite</i>		Rank
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	
1. The students are satisfied with the overall quality of academic support and guidance provided within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.45	TVGE	4.16	TGE	4.31	TVGE	2
2. There efficient mechanisms in place to address students' queries, concerns, and issues related to the computer system servicing specialization on time.	4.12	TGE	4.18	TGE	4.15	TGE	6
3. The school accommodate students' individual learning needs and preferences within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.23	TVGE	4.02	TGE	4.13	TGE	7
4. The school provide access to modern facilities and resources that enhance the learning experience for students pursuing the computer system servicing specialization.	4.25	TVGE	4.10	TGE	4.18	TGE	5
5. The students are satisfied with the availability of extracurricular activities, workshops, and industry-related events that complement the computer system servicing specialization.	3.40	TGE	4.19	TGE	3.80	TGE	10
6. The school proactively seeks feedback from students and faculty to continuously improve the quality of education within the computer system servicing specialization.	3.60	TGE	4.39	TVGE	4.00	TGE	9
7. The students were provided with opportunities for personalized career guidance, job placement assistance, and internships relevant to the computer system servicing specialization.	4.00	TGE	4.40	TVGE	4.20	TVGE	3
8. The school ensures that course materials, assignments, and assessments are aligned with the learning objectives and industry expectations of the computer system servicing specialization.	4.35	TVGE	4.34	TVGE	4.35	TVGE	1
9. There established mechanisms for students to provide feedback on the teaching methods, course content, and overall learning experience within the computer system servicing specialization.	4.00	TGE	4.38	TVGE	4.19	TGE	4
10. The school tracks the success and performance of graduates from the computer system servicing specialization in terms of employment opportunities and industry recognition.	4.00	TGE	4.22	TVGE	4.11	TGE	8
Overall weighted mean	4.04	TGE	4.24	TVGE	4.14	TGE	

As shown in Table 9, the teacher rated the four indicators on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of service quality as to a very great extent as manifested by the weighted mean of 4.45, 4.23, 4.25, and 4.35; whereas, indicators 2, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10 rated to a great extent as implied by the weighted means of 4.12, 3.40, 3.60, 4.00, 4.00, and 4.00, resulting in an overall weighted mean of 4.04 and verbally interpreted as to a great extent.

On the other hand, the student respondents rated five of the indicators as to a very great extent as noted by the weighted means of 4.39, 4.40, 4.34, 4.38, and 4.22. Nevertheless, indicators 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 were rated as to a great extent with a weighted mean of 4.16, 4.18, 4.02, 4.10, and 4.19. It resulted in an overall weighted mean of 4.24 and was interpreted as to a very great extent.

In entirety, the teacher and student respondents rated the indicators in on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization in terms of service quality as to a great extent; indicator 8 "The school ensures that course materials, assignments, and assessments are aligned with the learning objectives and industry expectations of the computer system servicing specialization." (WM = 4.35) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 1; indicator 1 "The students are satisfied with the overall quality of academic support and guidance provided within the computer system servicing specialization." (WM = 4.31) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 2; indicator 3 "The school accommodate students' individual learning needs and preferences within the computer system servicing specialization." (WM = 4.20) rated to a very great extent as rank no. 3; indicator 9 "There established mechanisms for students to provide feedback on the teaching methods, course content, and overall learning experience within the computer system servicing specialization." (WM = 4.19) rated to a great extent and ranked no. 4; indicator 4 "The school provide access to modern facilities and resources that enhance the learning experience for students pursuing the computer system servicing specialization." (WM

= 4.18) rated to a great extent as rank no. 5; indicator 2 “The computer system servicing specialization perceived as competitive and aligned with industry demands by potential employers and hiring managers.” (WM = 4.15) rated to a great extent and ranked no. 6; indicator 3 “The school accommodate students' individual learning needs and preferences within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.13) rated to a great extent as rank no. 7; indicator 10 “There efficient mechanisms in place to address students' queries, concerns, and issues related to the computer system servicing specialization on time.” (WM = 4.11) rated to a great extent and ranked as no. 8; indicator 6 “The school proactively seeks feedback from students and faculty to continuously improve the quality of education within the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 4.00) rated to a great extent as rank no. 9, and lastly, indicator 5 “The students are satisfied with the availability of extracurricular activities, workshops, and industry-related events that complement the computer system servicing specialization.” (WM = 3.80) rated to a great extent and ranked as no. 10, respectively.

In conclusion, the striking consensus between teacher and student respondents, who both rated the school's capability in offering computer system servicing as a specialization to a great extent in terms of service quality, as indicated by the impressive overall composite weighted mean of 4.14, reflected the institution's unwavering commitment to delivering excellence in education. This harmonious evaluation underscored the school's dedication to providing not just content knowledge but also a high-quality educational experience that met or exceeded the expectations of its stakeholders. The emphasis on service quality was crucial in preparing students for careers in computer system servicing, as it ensured they receive the necessary support, resources, and guidance to excel in their studies and future professional endeavors.

Furthermore, the findings highlighted the school's effectiveness in fostering an environment that prioritizes student satisfaction and success. The high ratings from both teacher and students on service quality underscored the institution's ability to create a supportive and conducive learning atmosphere. This, in turn, contributes to the overall positive reputation of the school and was likely to attract more students aspiring to specialize in computer system servicing. In summary, the results validated the school's commitment to providing a high standard of service quality, which was essential for both the academic growth and future careers of its students, solidifying its position as a reputable institution in the field of computer system servicing education.

The result adhered to what Famor (2005) stated that the use of ICT in education has become a critical factor to ensure that the country's workforce is skilled and prepared to meet the challenges of development and global employment opportunities.

Table 10. Summary of Respondents Assessment on the Extent of the Capability of the School in Offering Computer System Servicing as a Specialization

Indicators	Teacher		Student		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Knowledge	4.05	TGE	4.31	TVGE	4.18	TGE	1
2. Delivery	3.88	TGE	4.29	TVGE	4.09	TGE	3.5
3. Communication	4.02	TGE	4.16	TGE	4.09	TGE	3.5
4. Perception	3.94	TGE	4.07	TGE	4.01	TGE	5
5. Service Quality	4.04	TGE	4.24	TVGE	4.14	TGE	2
Overall weighted mean	3.99	TGE	4.21	TVGE	4.10	TGE	

Table 10 indicated the summary of assessment of teacher respondents on the extent of the capability of the school in offering Computer System Servicing as a specialization. It could be deduced from the data that the teacher rated all the indicators which are knowledge, delivery, communication, perception, and service quality as to a great extent as manifested by their respective weighted mean of 4.05, 3.88, 4.02, 3.94, and 4.04 and thus, yielded an overall weighted mean of 3.99 and was verbally interpreted as to a great extent.

Even so, the student respondents rated knowledge, delivery, and service quality as to a very great extent as shown by their respective weighted mean of 4.31, 4.29, and 4.24. Nonetheless, they rated communication and perception rated to a great extent with their weighted mean of 4.16 and 4.07. However, it yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.21 and interpreted as to a very great extent.

Together, in totality, the teacher and student respondents rated the indicators on the on the extent of the capability of the school in offering Computer System Servicing as a specialization as to a great extent, “knowledge” (WM = 4.18) as rank no. 1; “service quality” (WM = 4.14) as rank no. 2; “delivery” and “communication” (WM = 4.09) as rank no. 3.5, and lastly, “perception” (WM = 4.01) as rank no. 5, respectively.

The composite weighted mean score of 4.10, indicating that both teacher and student respondents perceived the extent of the school's capability in offering computer system servicing as a specialization to be at a great extent across various dimensions such as knowledge, delivery, communication, perception, and service quality, was a significant and positive finding. This robust consensus reflected the institution's well-rounded excellence in all critical aspects of its computer system servicing program. It suggested that the school excelled not only in imparting knowledge but also in effectively delivering that knowledge, maintaining open lines of communication, shaping positive perceptions, and ensuring high-quality service throughout the educational journey.

The collective perception of a great extent of capability across these dimensions was not only a testament to the school's commitment to providing top-notch education but also a strong indicator of its potential to attract and retain students who are passionate about specializing in computer system servicing. This perception, when combined with tangible educational outcomes, could solidify the

school's reputation in the field and contribute to its long-term success. Furthermore, the findings provided valuable insights for the school's continuous improvement efforts. By recognizing their strengths in these areas, the institution could build upon them and identified areas for further enhancement, ultimately benefiting both current and future students pursuing computer system servicing as their specialization.

The result was in consonance to what was stated by Asan (2003) that the use computer in education opens a new area of knowledge and offers a tool that has potential to change some of the existing educational methods.

Subproblem No. 3. What is the significant difference in the implementation of the computer system servicing specialization of schools about the assessment of staff and students?

Table 11. Result of Significant Difference

Indicators	Teacher		Students		Computed t-value	t-ration Decision	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation			
1. Knowledge	4.15	0.3375	4.32	0.1185	13.7539	Reject Ho	Significant
2. Delivery	3.88	0.3522	4.29	0.1318	19.8112	Reject Ho	Significant
3. Communication	4.02	0.6039	4.17	0.1503	4.4407	Reject Ho	Significant
4. Perception	3.94	0.4345	4.07	0.2997	4.2977	Reject Ho	Significant
5. Service Quality	4.04	0.3264	4.24	0.1327	10.2731	Reject Ho	Significant
Overall	4.01	0.4109	4.22	0.1666	10.5153	Reject Ho	Significant

Degrees of freedom = 587
Critical value of $t_{.05} = 1.960$

It could be gleaned from the data in Table 11, after the obtained values from the indicators was subjected to statistical analysis, it resulted to a computed t-value of 13.7539 (knowledge), 19.8112 (Delivery), 4.4407 (Communication), 4.2977 (Perception), and 10.2731 (Service Quality). Hence, yielded an overall computed t-value of 10.5153 which found to be of greater than the critical value of 1.960 at 0.05 level of significance with 587 degrees of freedom. The statistical decision was to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, verbally interpreted as significant.

Since the study failed to accept the null hypothesis, there was a clear indication that there was a significant difference between the assessment of the teachers and students in terms of knowledge, delivery, communication, perception, and service quality on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization.

This implied that the teachers do not concur with the assessment of the students in terms of knowledge, delivery, communication, perception, and service quality on the extent of the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization.

The disconnection between the assessments of teachers and students regarding the school's capability in offering computer system servicing as a specialization was a multifaceted issue. It underscored the importance of effective communication and feedback mechanisms within educational institutions. While students' assessments reflected their immediate experiences and expectations, teachers often take a broader, long-term view of program effectiveness and industry alignment. Bridging this gap required a holistic approach that involved reviewing the curriculum for relevance, enhancing teaching methods, and engaging industry experts for validation. Moreover, fostering transparent communication channels and regularly soliciting student feedback can provide insights into areas that needed improvement, ensuring that the program evolved to meet both student needs and industry standards. Ultimately, addressing this discrepancy was essential to create a more responsive and effective educational environment that aligns with the demands of computer system servicing as a specialized field.

Conclusions

In light of the findings, the following conclusions were formulated:

A significant and encouraging finding was that both school staff and student respondents believe the school was very capable of providing computer system servicing as a specialization across a wide range of dimensions, including knowledge, delivery, communication, perception, and service quality.

The school personnel did not concur with the assessment of the students in terms of Knowledge, Delivery, Communication, Perception, and Service Quality on the extent is the capability of the school in offering computer system servicing as a specialization.

The school personnel and students encountered problems on the instructional materials and teachers on the implementation of the computer system servicing specialization.

The importance of an action plan in enhancing the implementation of the computer system servicing specialization could not be overstated. It served as a strategic guide that not only outlines the objectives but also details the steps required to achieve them. This level of clarity was crucial in ensuring that efforts are well-coordinated, resources are effectively utilized, and timelines are adhered to, leading to a more efficient and successful program. Additionally, an action plan promotes accountability, allowing stakeholders to monitor progress, identify obstacles, and make informed decisions to continually refine and elevate the quality of education offered in

this specialization. Ultimately, the presence of a well-structured action plan underscored the commitment to providing students with a top-notch education that aligns with industry standards and equips them for success in the ever-evolving field of computer system servicing.

In consideration of the findings obtained and conclusions made, along with the limitations that the study had conceived, the following are recommended:

The action plan is recommended to be utilized to gauge its effectiveness to address the gap between the existing challenges in terms of implementation and the possible opportunity for its improvement. School administrators can look on the key indicators to enhance instructional delivery and improve the quality of the Computer Systems Servicing (CSS) program offering.

Teachers can also look on to how the action plan can be a means to further analyze the needs of the learners especially the CSS program maximizes the learning experiences of the learners with the use of technology and acquiring necessary knowledge and enhancing ICT.

Students can also consider the existing learning paradigm of CSS in order for them to track their academic journey on their chosen program and evaluate themselves in terms of the knowledge acquisition and skill development with the help of their schools as learning environment.

Since the sample size of this study was small, it could be recommended that future researchers can expound on the context of this study considering a larger population and expanding the locale of the study given that other than the District VI Manila, there are other schools offering the CSS as program for their prospective students. They can also consider other factors that affect the overall teaching-learning experience which was not part of the pentapartite gap analysis that this study had utilized.

References

- Advameg Inc. (2024). Gap Analysis. <https://www.referenceforbusiness.com/management/Ex-Gov/Gap-Analysis.html>
- AMA Online University (2021). TVL – Information and Communication Technology (ICT Strand). <https://www.onlineshs.com/information-and-communication-technology/>
- Continu Inc. (2023). Knowledge Gap Analysis. <https://www.continu.com/elearning-glossary/knowledge-gap-analysis>
- Department of Education (2024). What is K-12 Program. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/k-12/>
- Department of Education Manila (2024). Directory of Schools. <https://manila.deped.gov.ph/directory>
- Hayes, A. (2023). What Is a Gap Analysis?. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/g/gap-analysis.asp>
- Help Desk Migration (2024). Service Gap Analysis 101: Reshape Your Service Strategy. <https://help-desk-migration.com/service-gap>
- Juan, L. (2014). Literature Review of the Classifications of "Needs" in Needs Analysis Theory. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies* 2 (3). <http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.2n.3p.12>
- Llego, M.A. (2023). Specialized Subjects for TVL Track: ICT Strand. *TeacherPH*. <https://www.teacherph.com/specialized-subjects>
- Neve, S. (2024). The Perception Gap: Can we ever really know what users want? *Conversion*. <https://conversion.com/blog/the-perception-gap-can-we-ever-really-know-what>
- Que, E. N. (2021). Sustaining Successful ICT Integration in Remote Rural Schools. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. 29 (3).
- Sindayen, C. D. & De Leon, R. C. (2023). Lived Experiences of Public School Teachers in Teaching Computer System Servicing in the New Normal. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews* 4 (8). <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V4ISSUE8/IJRPR16102.pdf>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Dominic T. Urgelles

National University – Philippines

Marycris V. Urgelles

Mariano Marcos Memorial High School

Department of Education – Philippines